

Magneto-photoelectro

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Abstract- Making modifications in the setup used to study photoelectric effect. Which can be used for converting light energy to mechanical work done.

Index Terms- Photoelectric effect, Photoelectric plate, electrons, Photons, energy.

WORKING OF PHOTOELECTRIC EFFECT:

When a polarized light strikes a photoelectric plate, the plate emits electron.

The light hitting the plate carries photons with it (According to Einstein's postulate of quantization of energy).

These photons are massless packs of energy.

The energy of the photons is transferred to the electron present in the outermost shell of the metal atom.

When the electron gets enough energy to jump away from the range of its nucleus, it comes to the surface of the metal.

The additional energy transferred is then converted as kinetic energy.

This Kinetic energy is utilized by the electron to flow in the medium.

Equation Form:

$$E_p = \phi + \text{K.E.}$$

Here,

E_p is energy of photon,

Φ is work function (energy required to set electron free from its atom),

K.E. is the additional energy left converted to Kinetic Energy

Fig.1

UPGRADES TO BE MADE:

- Replace the positive plate with the same photoelectric plate.
- Replace the battery with an A/C supply.
- Incident a light of same intensity, color and frequency on the new plate
- Install two very thin bar magnets at the middle of the plates such that they are perpendicular to the flow of current.
- The two magnets should be at a particular distance away from the electric flow.
- They should face each other with same polarity.

ASSUMPTIONS BEHIND THE CONSTRUCTION:

As the positive plate is replaced with a photoelectric plate and incident with the same light, the electrons emitted from the plate will move towards the other photoelectric plate.

This will go on until the other plate acts as a positive end.

We have installed an AC supply, therefore the plate acts as a positive side for a while but as soon as the current alternates the process becomes reversed.

This results in formation of an electron cloud between the two plates which moves back and fro as the charge on plates change.

As the electrons are moving, a magnetic field is produced (according to right hand thumb rule).

In this case the direction of current is changing constantly this results in the change of polarity at the sides of the generated magnetic field

Generated magnetic fields

Fig.2

These changing magnetic poles will cause a movement in the bar magnets
 These movements can be further amplified and can be used effectively.

MODIFIED SETUP:

Fig.3

Magnets (red bars)
Photoelectric plate (green colored)
Incident light (blue color)
Cloud of electrons (golden color spheres)
The bars which are holding the magnet should have a slippery material such as grease or oil.
This will allow the magnets to show their movement effectively.

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